
Assessment of Antidiabetic Drugs Utilization Patterns in Diabetic Patients with Nephropathy in a Tertiary Healthcare Facility

Shuaibu Aliyu^{1*}, Abdulkadir Umar Zezi², Mohammad Garba Magaji², and Fatima Bello³

¹Department of Clinical Pharmacy and Pharmacy Practice, Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria – Nigeria

²Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria – Nigeria

³Department of Medicine, Ahmadu Bello University (ABU), Zaria – Nigeria

*Corresponding author, E-mail: ashuaibu@abu.edu.ng, [doi.org.10.55639/njpbr.1051.005](https://doi.org/10.55639/njpbr.1051.005)

Abstract

The presence of nephropathy in diabetic patients may complicate the management of diabetes. Appropriate use of drugs is essential in achieving optimal outcomes in such patients. Therefore, this study was aimed at assessing antidiabetic drugs utilization patterns in diabetic patients with nephropathy at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, ABUTH, Zaria, Nigeria. Retrospective and cross-sectional research designs were used to collect data on drug use indicators from the prescriptions of patients who met the eligibility criteria. In addition, patient care indicators were assessed prospectively while patients were being attended to by physicians and pharmacists, respectively. Data were collected from 600 prescriptions over a period of 29 days and the results were presented using descriptive statistics. An average of 1.3 antidiabetic drugs per prescription was observed. Most of the drugs (88.6 %) were prescribed using generic names, 42.3 % and 62.3 % accounted for encounters with antibiotics and injections, respectively. Insulin (16.96 DDD/1000 diabetic patients with renal impairment) was 1.8 times more utilized than oral hypoglycaemic agents (OHAs). Among the OHAs, metformin (5.14 DDD/1000) was the most utilized, followed by glibenclamide (2.76 DDD/1000), gliclazide (1.04 DDD/1000), pioglitazone (0.37 DDD/1000) and gliclazide (0.09 DDD/1000). The average cost of a prescription in the facility was N13,423.94. In conclusion, it was observed that insulin was the most utilized antidiabetic agent among the population of patients in the facility and the cost of a prescription is high. Therefore, interventions to curtail the cost of the drugs, Social Health Insurance Programme should be adopted in the facility as most of the patients were not employed.

Keywords: ABUTH, antidiabetic, drug utilization, drug use indicators, metformin, prescriptions

Introduction

Globally, diabetes is considered a progressive disorder and the leading cause of diabetic nephropathy which occurs in 20 – 40% of patients with diabetes and it is the single leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) (American Diabetes Association, 2013; WHO, 1999). In addition, people with type 2 diabetes and diabetic nephropathy are at increased risk for developing many other diabetic complications (Deshpande *et al.*, 2008).

The diabetes statistics of the International Diabetic Federation (IDF) showed that Nigeria has the highest number of people living with diabetes in Africa with an estimated 2,819,100 cases in 2010 which is projected to be 6,630,300 in the year 2045 (International Diabetes Federation, 2019). Since diabetes is considered the major cause of nephropathy in diabetic patients, this may suggest that Nigeria has the highest number of diabetic patients with nephropathy on the continent.

Metformin is the drug of first choice for type 2 diabetics even in cases with renal impairments as contained in most good practice recommendations (Bonnet *et al.*, 2011). Metformin, compared with other antidiabetic agents, is considered the drug that has been shown to reduce all-cause and cardiovascular mortality in patients with DM as reported in the UK Prospective Diabetic Study (UKPDS) (American Diabetes Association, 1998). However, renal tubular secretion is the major route of elimination of metformin. Therefore, any compromise in renal function may increase the risk for the development of Metformin Associated Lactic Acidosis (MALA) and other side effects (Setter *et al.*, 2003). It has been reported that metformin-induced lactic acidosis carries a mortality rate of up to 50% (Nawaz *et al.*, 1998) even with prompt treatment. Therefore, this study sought to assess the antidiabetic utilization among diabetic patients with nephropathy in Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria, Nigeria as there is a paucity of studies on the subject in this facility. This is necessary as understanding drug utilization patterns can provide valuable insights into current clinical practices, promote evidence-based decision-making, enhance patient safety, and guide the development of therapeutic protocols tailored for this specific population.

Methods

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for the research was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTHZ/HREC/X08/2016) and the

National Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC/10/12/2015) before the commencement of this study.

Study Setting and Population

The study site was Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital Shika, Zaria, Kaduna State. The study was carried out among diabetes patients with nephropathy attending the diabetes clinic of the hospital.

Research Design

Both retrospective and prospective cross-sectional research designs were employed for this research.

Eligibility Criteria

Only prescriptions of diabetic patients with renal impairment who had at least one antidiabetic medication prescribed and diabetic patients with an established diagnosis of nephropathy who reached the age of at least 18 years and who were receiving care for at least 3 months in the facility were included in this study. However, inpatients, newly diagnosed patients, patients less than 18 years old and those who declined to participate in the study were excluded.

Data Collection

A descriptive retrospective study was used to assess data on prescribing and complementary indicators from case folders that met the eligibility criteria of this study. Data were collected on a sample of 600 patients' folders of diabetic patients with nephropathy as recommended by the WHO (1993) guideline for drug utilization. In addition, a prospective study was also undertaken on a purposive sample of 250 diabetic patients with nephropathy to determine the patients' care indicators

(average consulting and dispensing time, percentage of drugs dispensed, and adequate knowledge of correct dosage). Patient's prescription plans were copied out in pre-designed data collection forms adapted from WHO guidelines on how to investigate drug use in health facilities. The data obtained were sorted and classified according to the WHO ATC/DDD (Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical/ Defined Daily Dose) Classification System (WHO, 1993). Costs/DDD were calculated in Naira using

Prescribing indicators:

1. average number of antidiabetic drugs per encounter

$$= \frac{\text{total number of different antidiabetic drugs prescribed}}{\text{number of encounters surveyed}}$$
2. percentage of antidiabetics prescribed by generic name

$$= \frac{\text{number of antidiabetics prescribed by generic name}}{\text{total number of drugs prescribed}} \times 100\%$$
3. percentage of encounters with an antibiotic prescribed

$$= \frac{\text{number of antibiotics prescribed}}{\text{total number of drugs prescribed}} \times 100\%$$
4. percentage of encounters with an injection prescribed

$$= \frac{\text{number of patients encountered with injection}}{\text{total number of encounters surveyed}} \times 100$$
5. percentage of drugs prescribed from the essential drug list

$$= \frac{\text{number of products prescribed from the essential drug list of the hospital}}{\text{total number of drugs prescribed}} \times 100$$

Patient care indicators:

1. average consultation time = $\frac{\text{total time for a series of consultations}}{\text{actual number of consultations}}$
2. average dispensing time = $\frac{\text{total time for dispensing drugs to a series of patients}}{\text{number of encounters}}$
3. percentage of drugs actually dispensed

$$= \frac{\text{number of drugs actually dispensed}}{\text{total number of drugs prescribed}} \times 100\%$$

the hospital price list. Data were collected between January 2015 and May 2017. All the calculations were done according to the WHO (1993) guidelines for investigating drug use in health facilities as illustrated in the following equations. Drug utilization 90% (DU90%) was calculated by ranking (in descending order) the drugs by the value of defined daily doses (DDD) and determining how many drugs accounted for the 90% segment. The results were presented descriptively

$$4. \text{ percentage of patients' knowledge of correct dosage} \\ = \frac{\text{number of patients who can adequately report the dosage schedule for all drugs}}{\text{total number of patients interviewed}} \\ \times 100\%$$

Facility indicators:

1. The availability of a copy of EDL: By stating yes (or) no.
2. availability of key drugs

$$= \frac{\text{number of specified products actually in stock}}{\text{total number of drugs on the checklist}} \times 100\%$$

Complementary indicators:

1. average drug cost per encounter = $\frac{\text{total cost of all drugs prescribed}}{\text{number of encounters surveyed}}$
2. percentage of drug costs spent on injection

$$= \frac{\text{cost of injections prescribed}}{\text{total drug cost}} \times 100$$

The formulas for other parameters are shown below:

- a. DDD/1000/day: The DDD/1000/day was calculated as follows,

$$\frac{\text{Total amount of drugs used during study period(mg, units)} \times 1000}{\text{DDD (mg, units)} \times \text{Duration under review} \times \text{total sample size}}$$

- b. Cost Per DDD: The Cost Per DDD was calculated as follows,

$$\frac{\text{Cost of one tablet or vial of insulin (₦)} \times \text{DDD(mg, units)}}{\text{Strength of one tablet or vial of insulin(mg, unit)}}$$

Results

A total of 600 case folders of diabetic patients with renal impairment between the months of January 2015 and May 2017 inclusive were reviewed. It was found that 247 (41%) and 353 (59%) were male and female respectively. An average number of all drug classes of 3.9 and 1.4 of antidiabetics were found per prescription. Most of the drugs were prescribed using generic names (88.6%). There a high rate of antibiotics (42.3%) prescriptions among the sample of prescriptions assessed, injections accounted for (62.3%) of the total number of drugs, and 97.91% of all the drugs were prescribed from the

Nigerian National Essential Drug List except pioglitazone. The average consultation and dispensing time were 13 and 5 minutes respectively. Most of the drugs (89%) were dispensed to the patients and the majority of the patients (91%) had adequate knowledge of the correct doses of their medications. There was the availability of essential drug lists and hospital formulary in this facility, and all the key antidiabetics were available in the pharmacy. The average cost of filling antidiabetic prescriptions was ₦1,762:86 (US\$4.31), and 92% of the cost of the drugs was spent on injections (Table 1). Finally, the DU90% indicates that insulins and metformin account for the most

utilized antidiabetic agents in the facility while the beyond DU90% segment accounts for the drugs that were used

either as an alternative option or in combination with other drugs (Table 2).

Table 1: Drug Use Indicators among Patients with Diabetic Nephropathy in ABUTH
During the Period under Review

Core Indicators	Value	WHO/INRUD Ideal Value
Prescribing Indicators		
Average number of antidiabetics prescribed (n)	1.4	1.6-1.8
Average number of drugs prescribed (n)	3.9	1.6-1.8
Generics (%)	88.6	100
Antibiotics (%)	42.3	20-26.8
Injections (%)	62.3	13.4-24.1
National Essential Drug List (%)	97.91	100
Patient Care Indicators		
Average consulting time (min)	13	>10
Average dispensing time (min)	5	>1.5
Drugs dispensed (%)	89	100
Adequate knowledge of correct dosage (%)	91	100
Facility Indicators		
Availability of Essential drug list	Yes	Yes
Key drugs available (%)	100	100
Complementary Indicators		
Average cost of antidiabetics per prescription (₦)	1,763:86	-
Percentage Cost of injection	92	-

WHO/INRUD means World Health Organization/International Network for Rational Use of Drugs; n, number; %, per cent; min, minute

Table 2: Antidiabetic Drug Utilization Pattern among Diabetic Patients with Nephropathy in the Facility During the Period under Review

ATC code	Drug prescribed	Percentage	DDD/1000 inhabitants/day	Cost/DDD (₦)
A10AB	Fast acting insulin	30.86	19.67	110:00
A10BA02	Metformin	28.78	1.10	57:20
A10AC	Intermediate acting insulin	24.28	15.47	154:88
Within DU90% segment		83.92	36.24	322:08
A10BB12	Glimepiride	7.72	0.20	101:63
A10BB01	Glibenclamide	5.79	0.07	23:22
A10BG03	Pioglitazone	2.09	0.05	39:50
A10BB09	Gliclazide	0.48	0.01	75:60
Beyond DU90% segment		16.08	0.33	239:95
Total = within DU90% + beyond DU90%		100.00	36.57	562:03

ATC, Anatomical and Therapeutic Classification; DDD, Defined Daily Dose; n, number of prescriptions; DU90%, 90 percent drug utilization

Discussion

The high average number of drugs per prescription observed in this study was not surprising as diabetic patients with comorbidities may require multiple medications to achieve the desired treatment goal (Eze and Odunayo, 2010; Patel *et al.*, 2013). Based on our search, there is no evidence in the literature on the assessment of drug utilization among diabetic nephropathic patients in Nigeria. However, a study on diabetic patients by Adibe *et al.* (2009) reported an average of 2.6 in their study in southeast Nigeria. In contrast, Ogbonna and Ezenduka (2014) reported a higher value of 4 in Nnamdi Azikiwe University Teaching Hospital at Nnewi, Anambra State, southeast Nigeria. Eze and Odunayo, (2010) reported an average of 4.7 in Olabisi Onabanjo University Teaching Hospital, Ogun State,

southwest Nigeria. Also, Odusanya, (2000) reported an average of 3.5 in Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Furthermore, Chedi, *et al.*, (2015) reported a higher value in Northern Nigeria. An average number of drugs in a prescription is a measure of polypharmacy (Vaniya *et al.*, 2016) which is associated with increased incidence of drug-drug interaction, therapeutic error, contraindication, and adverse drug reactions (Bashrahil, 2010; Tamuno and Fadare, 2012). Furthermore, polypharmacy in a prescription and its associated clinical consequences may eventually lead to medication non-adherence, a decrease in treatment outcomes, and an increased overall cost of care (Upadhyay *et al.*, 2007; Ghimire *et al.*, 2009). It is preferable to keep the number of drugs per prescription as low as possible, to reduce

the risk of such consequences (Vaniya *et al.*, 2016). Polypharmacy can further be minimized by adhering to the standard treatment guidelines when prescribing (Chareonkul *et al.*, 2002), educational interventions to the prescribers (Sipcic *et al.*, 2007), and the use of a fixed-dose combination to reduce pill burden (Blix, 2016; Eze and Odunayo, 2010).

The percentage of drugs prescribed by generic name accounted for 88.6%, slightly below the 100% recommended by the WHO/INRUD. Deviation from the recommended value is an indication that prescribers dwelled on branded products. This was obvious in the facility during the study period where it was observed that the prescribers had a high preference for a particular brand of metformin sustained-release formulation. The value observed for generic prescriptions in the facility was satisfactory and better than the findings of other studies in Nigeria. For example, Eze and Odunayo (2010), Adibe and colleagues, Babalola and colleagues, Ogbonna and Ezenduka (2014), Tamuno and Fadare (2012), and Ezenduka and colleagues reported 40.1, 72.5, 69.8, 58, 42.7 and 83% respectively for generic prescription in Nigeria. Furthermore, findings from other countries were as follows: Acharya and colleagues (2013) reported 4.3% in India, Desalegn (2013) reported 98.7% in Ethiopia, Akl and colleagues (2014) reported 95.4% in Egypt, Afriyie and Raymond (2014) reported 62.6% in Ghana. In some situations, generic prescribing is mandatory especially for drugs with narrow therapeutic windows (Lenjisa and Fereja, 2014). Furthermore, generic prescribing allows flexibility of stocking and dispensing various brands of a particular drug that are cheaper and as

effective as proprietary brands (Eze and Odunayo, 2010). Similarly, generic prescription helps with improved communication and clarity among healthcare providers (Atif *et al.*, 2016) and also reduces the possibility of prescription errors (Shankar *et al.*, 2007). It also allows the pharmacist to maintain a more economic stock control system based on a smaller range of reasonably priced drugs (Chedi *et al.*, 2015). The possible reasons for a low generic prescription from the literature include lucrative advertisements by the pharmaceutical sales representatives, insufficient availability of a generic drug in pharmacy (Ashar *et al.*, 2016), clinical experience of prescribers with a particular brand, and lack the same confidence in generic drugs (Vaniya *et al.*, 2016) and prescribers' belief that the brand names are easier to remember as well as the frequent use of brand names during their training (Chedi *et al.*, 2015).

Similarly, the percentage of encounters with antibiotics in this facility was also above the WHO/INRUD cut-off value. This is not surprising as diabetic patients are prone to infections in comparison to the general population as demonstrated by one of the largest systemic reviews and meta-analyses of observational studies on the association between diabetes mellitus and incidents of infections (Abu-ashour *et al.*, 2017). The high risk of infection in diabetic patients has been attributed to the reduced response of T cells, neutrophil function, and disorders of humoral immunity (Casqueiro *et al.*, 2012). Further to this, diabetic foot ulcer is one of the common complication of diabetes mellitus which is usually polymicrobial caused by an array of microorganisms such as aerobic gram-positive cocci like *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative

bacilli (*Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*), and anaerobes (Saseedhara *et al.*, 2017). In addition, Hamilton and colleagues (2013) reported in their study that patients with diabetes had doubled the incidence of hospitalization for infectious diseases vs that of matched non-diabetic controls. These may necessitate the use of antibiotics to curtail the scourge of infections in such patients. Afriyie and Raymond (2014) in Ghana, Assen and Abrha (2014) in Ethiopia had reported high use of antibiotics in their respective studies similar to the finding of this study. Studies have demonstrated that inappropriate use of antibiotics can lead to serious clinical problems, such as the emergence of drug resistance, super-infection, allergies, and other health hazards (Bashrahil, 2007). Inappropriate use of antibiotics may also necessitate the need to use more expensive antibiotics to treat common and life-threatening infections which may increase the cost of filling a prescription and eventually affect treatment outcome due to non-adherence. This study suggested that the WHO/INRUD cut-off value for antibiotics should be reviewed upward since it is known that population of diabetic patients are more prone to infections compared with the general population.

The percentage of encounters with injections of 62.3% observed in this study was higher than the recommended WHO/INRUD value of 13.4 – 24.1% and was also higher when compared with various studies on drug utilization in the country. This was also consistent with the findings of Babalola and coworkers in this country. In contrast, Eze and Odunayo, (2010), Adibe *et al.* (2009), Tamuno and Fadare, (2012) and Odusanya, (2000)

reported 2.1, 7.9, 4.0 and 13.8% respectively. The values reported by these authors were even lower than the WHO ideal values for drug utilization. The high usage of injection observed in the facility could be attributed to the frequent use of parenteral antibiotics for the treatment of infections as well as insulin injection which was the most utilized antidiabetic drug among the population of patients in the facility which accounted for 55.14% for both fast and intermediate-acting insulin.

All the prescriptions in the facility were in line with the national essential drug lists. Key drugs and essential drug lists were also available in the facility as recommended by WHO/INRUD norms. Adibe and co-workers, Tamuno and Fadare, (2012), and Sau and co-workers in their respective study, reported a similar trend with the findings of our study. The WHO advocates that all prescriptions should be done according to the national essential drug list developed from the WHO essential drug list model which is being reviewed every two years since its inception in 1977. Compliance with the national essential drug list and availability of key drugs in the facility may reflect rational prescribing to such population of patients. According to the WHO essential drug policy, essential drugs serve the priority healthcare needs of the majority of patients at low cost to both the government and patients. Furthermore, the availability of key drugs in generic form depicts that there is the accessibility of drugs in the facility as suggested by WHO. It was further stated that governments at all levels, the private sector and civil society each has vital roles and responsibilities in achieving universal access and affordability to essential drugs which have

been considered as the fundamental human right (WHO, 2001).

The average consultation and dispensing times observed in this study were within the WHO/INRUD cut-off values for rational use of drugs. An optimal consultation time is required for proper history-taking, complete physical examination, and appropriate health education instructions (Aslam *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, an optimal dispensing time allows pharmacists to offer adequate drug information to patients about the correct dosage, side effects they may experience, adverse drug effects, and counselling, which in turn may enhance compliance with treatment and lead to better treatment outcomes (Mudenda *et al.*, 2016). The longer values for consultation and dispensing times observed in this study demonstrated that the facility had an adequate number of different healthcare personnel to cater to the healthcare needs of the patients. A study among the diabetic population in Nigeria by Adibe and co-workers has reported a similar trend with the findings of this study. The percentage of drugs actually dispensed and the patient's knowledge about the correct dosage were slightly below the recommended value. The shortfalls in the percentage of drugs dispensed to the patients could be attributed partly to stockout (Ezenduka *et al.*, 2014) and partly due to the financial status of the patients during clinic visits as well as patients' preference to buy their drugs outside the hospital pharmacy. Patients' knowledge of the correct dosage is essential for proper use of medication which may lead to better therapeutic outcomes. The high level of patients' knowledge of the correct dosage observed in this study could be attributed to the higher consultation and dispensing

times to the patients by the doctors and pharmacists respectively. Also, the dispensaries in the pharmacy department of the facility were fitted with counselling rooms where patients were being counselled on the proper use of their prescribed medication by the pharmacist in attendance.

The average cost of antidiabetics in a prescription was very high in this facility. This is not surprising as most of the prescriptions contained insulin which contributed to the higher share of the cost. Further to this, the finding of this study also revealed that injections carried 92% of the total cost of prescriptions. The cost of drugs (₦1,763:86 equivalent to US\$4:31) observed in this study is high compared with the finding of a study in the south-eastern part of the country where it has been reported ₦353 approximately US\$2.4 as an average cost of a prescription (Adibe *et al.*, 2009). However, the differences in cost may be attributed to exchange rates with time at the time for each study. By implication, the high cost of drug therapy may predispose patients to medication non-adherence and its devastating effects on the treatment outcomes.

The study demonstrated that metformin is the most utilized oral antidiabetics in the facility even though the majority of the patients had a contraindication to its use. In support of this, evidence from retrospective studies has demonstrated that metformin is still in use even in cases of contraindications (Moore, 2009) due to its numerous benefits on treatment outcomes (Díaz *et al.*, 2017). It is also an available, affordable, and well-tolerated drug.

Similar to metformin, insulin is the most utilized injectable antidiabetic in the facility. It is being used alone or in combination with other drugs (particularly

metformin). This is because insulin and its analogues are considered the preferred agents to achieve tight glycaemic control, particularly in hospitalized and diabetic patients with complications as recommended by the American Diabetes Association (ADA) guideline due to their benefits in improving treatment outcomes and the overall quality of life (Diabetes Care, 2018). In addition, it has been further suggested that many patients with type 2 diabetes eventually require and benefit from insulin therapy (American Diabetes Association, 2017). Similarly, studies on antidiabetic drug utilization had observed a shifting trend for the use of insulin therapy with other antidiabetic drugs among type 2 diabetic patients as reported by Agarwal and colleagues (2014) (43.6%), Ashar and colleagues, (57.69%), Upadhyay and colleagues, (41.07%), and Soumya and colleagues (2015), (42.1%). However, insulin should be used with caution in diabetic patients with nephropathy due to an increase in fluid retention which may further deteriorate the condition of such patients and the possible reason for the high use of insulin in the facility may be due to the belief of the clinicians that metformin may induce lactic acidosis to such patients and the need for tight glycaemic control for poorly controlled patients particularly inpatients.

The drug utilization 90% (DU90%) segment is the number of drugs that account for 90% of drug prescriptions (Igboeli *et al.*, 2010) after ranking the drugs used by volume of DDDs (Soe *et al.*, 2020). It has been described as an inexpensive, flexible, and simple method of assessing the quality of drug prescribing in routine healthcare (Bergman *et al.*, 1998; Igboeli *et al.*, 2010). The present study revealed that only fast-acting insulin,

metformin, and intermediate-acting insulin fall within the DU90% which conformed to the drug of the first choice for the treatment of diabetics with nephropathy according to the national and international treatment guidelines. This is an indication of rational utilization of antidiabetics in the population as the fewer the number of drugs within DU90% and adherence to standard treatment guidelines are suggestive of rational and quality use of medicines in a facility (Bergman *et al.*, 1998; Vlahovic-Palcevski *et al.*, 2002; Kulkarni *et al.*, 2016). In comparison, a study in the south-eastern part of the country reported metformin, glibenclamide, chlorpropamide, and fast-acting insulin as within the DU90% segment (Adibe *et al.*, 2009). In contrast to the within DU90% segment, beyond DU90% (DU10%) segment accounts for drugs that are not being used in large volume and are not a priority to be procured except on an emergency (Prihayati, 2019). The drugs that fall beyond DU90% observed in this study were glimepiride, glibenclamide, pioglitazone, and gliclazide. Management guidelines for diabetes have shown that drugs that fall beyond DU90% are often used in combination with either insulin or metformin for effective therapy. Furthermore, the cost/DDD within the DU90% segment for this study was found to be higher than the cost beyond the DU90% segment. The reverse of the case was expected as many high-volume medications are known to be not very expensive (Bergman *et al.*, 1998) and are used as a measure of the cost-effectiveness of a treatment (Elseviers *et al.*, 2016). The deviation in the cost/DDD could be attributed to the high utilization of insulin in the facility coupled with its high cost.

The study established that fast-acting insulin was the most utilized antidiabetic drug in the facility. Followed by metformin as the most widely used oral antidiabetic agent in the population of diabetic patients with nephropathy in this facility despite its associated risk for metformin-associated lactic acidosis. It is recommended that further study should be done to assess the safety of these drugs. Many formularies advised that insulin should be used with caution in diabetic patients with nephropathy due to an increase in fluid retention which may

further deteriorate the condition of such patients, while metformin is linked with the emergence of lactic acidosis in such patients.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledged the moral support of the Department of Clinical Pharmacy and Pharmacy Practice, ABU Zaria for the opportunity to conduct this study.

Conflict of interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

References

- Abu-ashour, W., Twells, L., Valcour, J., Randell, A., Donnan, J., Howse, P., and Gamble, J. (2017). The association between diabetes mellitus and incident infections: a systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *BMJ Open Diabetes Research and Care*, 5, e000336. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjdr-2016-000336>
- Acharya, K. G., Shah, K. N., Solanki, N. D., and Rana, D. A. (2013). Evaluation of antidiabetic prescriptions, cost and adherence to treatment guidelines: A prospective, cross-sectional study at a tertiary care teaching hospital. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy*, 4(4), 82–87. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0976-0105.121653>
- Adibe, M. O., Aguwa, C. N., Ukwue, C. V., Okonta, J. M., and Udeogaranya, P. O. (2009). Outpatient Utilization of Anti-diabetic Drugs in the South Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Drug Development and Research*, 1(1), 27–36.
- Afriyie, D. K. (2014). *Full Length Research Paper A description of the pattern of rational drug use in Ghana Police Hospital*. 3(1), 143–148.
- Agarwal, A. A., Jadhav, P. R., and Deshmukh, Y. A. (2014). Prescribing pattern and efficacy of antidiabetic drugs in maintaining optimal glycemic levels in diabetic patients. *Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacy*, 5(3), 79–83. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0976-0105.139731>
- Akl, O. A., Mahalli, A. A. El, Elkahky, A. A., and Salem, A. M. (2014). *WHO / INRUD drug use indicators at primary healthcare centers in Alexandria, Egypt*. 9, 54–64.
- American Diabetes Association. (1998). Implications of the United Kingdom Prospective Diabetes Study. *Diabetes Care*, 21(12), 2180–2184.
- American Diabetes Association. (2013). Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2013. *Diabetes Care*, 36(1), S12–S66. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc13-S011>

- American Diabetes Association. (2017). Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2017. *The Journal of Clinical and Applied Research and Education*, 40, S1–S133.
- Ashar, S. M., Hanif, A., Jadoon, A., Rehman, M., Ullah, N., Kamal, Z., Hussain, H., and Yasmeen, S. (2016). Assessment of Drug Use Pattern Using WHO Prescribing Indicators in the Medication Therapy of Indoor Diabetic Patients. *International Journal of Basic Medical Sciences and Pharmacy*, 6(1), 16–20.
- Aslam, A., Khatoon, S., Mehdi, M., Mumtaz, S., and Murtaza, B. (2016). *Evaluation of Rational Drug Use at Teaching Hospitals in Punjab*, 2(2), 54–57.
- Assen, A., and Abrha, S. (2014). *Assessment of Drug Prescribing Pattern in Dessie Referral Hospital, Dessie*. *International Journal of Pharma Sciences and Research*, 5(11), 777–781.
- Atif, M., Sarwar, M. R., Azeem, M., Umer, D., Rauf, A., Rasool, A., Ahsan, M., and Scahill, S. (2016). Assessment of WHO / INRUD core drug use indicators in two tertiary care hospitals of Bahawalpur, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Policy and Practice*, 9(27), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40545-016-0076-4>
- Babalola, C. P., Awoloye, S. A., Akinyemi, J. O., and Kotila, O. A. (2011). Evaluation of prescription pattern in Osun State (Southwest) Nigeria. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology*, 3(3), 94–98. <http://www.academicjournals.org/jphe>
- Bashrahil, K. A. (2007). Indicators of rational drug use and health services in Hadramout, Yemen. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 16(2), 151–155.
- Bergman, U., Popa, C., Tomson, Y., Wettermark, B., Einarson, T. R., Aberg, H., and Sjoqvist, F. (1998). Drug utilization 90 % - a simple method for assessing the quality of drug prescribing. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*, 54, 113–118.
- Bonnet, F., Gauthier, E., Gin, H., Hadjadj, S., Halimi, J.-M., Hannedouche, T., Rigalleau, V., Romand, D., Roussel, R., and Zaoui, P. (2011). Expert consensus on management of diabetic patients with impairment of renal function. *Diabetes and Metabolism*, 37, S1–S25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1262-3636\(11\)70961-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1262-3636(11)70961-2)
- Casqueiro, J., Casqueiro, J., and Alves, C. (2012). Infections in patients with diabetes mellitus: A review of pathogenesis. *Indian Journal of Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 16, S27–S36. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2230-8210.94253>
- Chareonkul, C., Khun, V. L., and Boonshuyar, C. (2002). Rational Drug Use in Cambodia: Study of Three Pilot Health Centers in Kampong Thom Province. *South East Asian J Trop Med Pub Health*, 33(2), 418–424.
- Chedi, B. A. Z., Abdu-aguye, I., and Kwanashie, H. O. (2015). Drug use pattern in out-patient children: A comparison between primary and secondary health care facilities in Northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology*, 9(4), 74–81. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJPP2014>.
- Desalegn, A. A. (2013). *Assessment of drug use pattern using WHO*

- prescribing indicators at Hawassa University teaching and referral hospital, south Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study.*
- Deshpande, A. D., Harris-Hayes, M., and Schootman, M. (2008). Epidemiology of Diabetes and Diabetes-Related Complications. *Physical Therapy*, 88(11), 1254–1264.
- Diabetes Care. (2018). Diabetes Care in the Hospital: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2018. *Diabetes Care*, 41(1), 144–151. <https://doi.org/10.2337/dc18-S014>
- Díaz, M. F., Valente, R. A., Mosquera, V. B., Abuward, I., Martínez, S. P., Ardha, N., Beloso, M. D., García, D. N., Martínez, T. C., Carbajal, D. G., and Rodríguez, C. D. (2017). *iMedPub Journals Metformin Challenges in Advanced Chronic Kidney Disease: A Promising Therapeutic Strategy*. 1–10.
- Elseviers, M., Wettermark, B., Almarsdóttir, A. B., Andersen, M., Benko, R., Bennie, M., Eriksson, I., Godman, B., Krska, J., Poluzzi, E., Taxis, K., Vlahović-Palčevski, V., and Stichele, R. Vander. (2016). *Drug Utilization Methods and*. John Wiley and Sons.
- Eze, U. I. H., and Odunayo, O. O. (2010). Evaluation of Drug Use among Diabetic Hypertensive Patients in a Teaching Hospital. *International Journal of Drug Development and Research*, 2(4), 703–710.
- Ezenduka, C. C., Ubochi, V. N., and Ogbonna, B. O. (2014). *The Utilization Pattern and Costs Analysis of Psychotropic Drugs at a Neuropsychiatric Hospital in Nigeria*. 4(3), 325–337.
- Ghimire, S., Bhandari, S., and Palaian, S. (2009.). *Students ' Corner A prospective surveillance of drug prescribing and dispensing in a teaching hospital in Western Nepal*. 59(10), 1–4.
- Hamilton, E. J., Martin, N., Makepeace, A., Sillars, B. A., Davis, W. A., and Davis, T. M. E. (2013). Incidence and Predictors of Hospitalization for Bacterial Infection in Community-Based Patients with Type 2 Diabetes: The Fremantle Diabetes Study. *PLoS One*, 8(3), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0060502>
- Igboeli, N. U., Ukwe, C. V., and Ekwunife, O. I. (2010). Increasing use of artemisinin-based combination therapy for treatment of malaria infection in Nigerian hospitals. *Pharmacy Practice (Internet)*, 8(4), 243–249.
- International Diabetes Federation. (2019). *IDF Diabetes Atlas Ninth Edition*.
- Kulkarni, D., Kokila, B. N., Sahu, S. K., and G, R. K. (2016). Drug utilization 90 %: an innovative method in assessing quality of drug prescription with specific reference to non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs prescription. *International Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacology*, 5(5), 1746–1751. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2319-2003.ijbcp20162893>
- Lenjisa, J. L., and Fereja, T. H. (2014). *A Retrospective Analysis of Prescribing Practices through WHO Prescribing Indicators at Four Selected Hospitals of West Ethiopia*. 6(4), 29–32. <https://doi.org/10.4172/1948-593X.1000105>
- Moore, K. G. (2009). *Metformin use in renal dysfunction: Is a serum creatinine threshold appropriate?* NOVEMBER.

- <https://doi.org/10.2146/ajhp080330>
- Mudenda, W., Chikatula, E., Chambula, E., Mwanashimbala, B., Chikuta, M., Masaninga, F., Songolo, P., Vwalika, B., Kachimba, J. S., Mufunda, J., and Mweetwa, B. (2016). Prescribing Patterns and Medicine Use at the University Teaching Hospital, Lusaka, Zambia. *Medical Journal of Zambia*, 43(2), 94–102.
- Nawaz, S., Cleveland, T., Gaines, P. A., and Chan, P. (1998). Clinical risk associated with contrast angiography in metformin treated patients: a clinical review. *Clinical Radiology*, 53(5), 342–344. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-9260\(98\)80005-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0009-9260(98)80005-6)
- Odo, H. O., Olotu, S. O., Agbonile, I. O., Esan, P. O., James, B. O., and Hillary, O. O. (2013). *Evaluation of the drug utilization pattern at a regional psychiatric hospital, in Benin city, Nigeria*. 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.4103/2045-080X.123222>
- Odusanya, O. O. (2000). Drug use indicators at a secondary health care facility in Lagos, Nigeria. *Journal of Community Medicine and Primary Health Care*, 16(1), 21–24.
- Ogbonna, B. O., and Ezenduka, C. C. (2014). Drug Use Indicators in Patients with Type 2 Diabetes in a Tertiary Healthcare Facility in Nigeria. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 6(11), 493–495.
- Patel, B., Oza, B., Patel, K. P., Malhotra, S. D., and Patel, V. J. (2013). *IJBPC International Journal of Basic and Clinical Pharmacology Research Article Pattern of antidiabetic drugs use in type-2 diabetic patients in a medicine outpatient clinic of a tertiary care teaching hospital*. 2(4), 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.5455/2319-2003.ijbcp20130826>
- Prihayati, A. (2019). Drug Utilization Pattern and Cost Estimates of Antihypertensive Drugs in Pharmacies under the National Health Insurance Program. *The 6th International Conference on Public Health*, 263–269. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26911/the6thicph-FP.04.06>
- Saseedharan, S., Sahu, M., Chaddha, R., and Pathrose, E. (2017). Epidemiology of diabetic foot infections in a reference tertiary hospital in India. *Brazilian Journal of Microbiology*, 49(2), 401–406. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bjm.2017.09.003>
- Setter, S. M., Iltz, J. L., Thams, J., and Campbell, R. K. (2003). Metformin hydrochloride in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus: A clinical review with a focus on dual therapy. *Clinical Therapeutics*, 25(12), 2991–3026. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2918\(03\)90089-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2918(03)90089-0)
- Shankar, P., Pai, R., Dubey, A., and Upadhyay, D. (2007). Prescribing patterns in the orthopaedics outpatient department in a teaching hospital in Pokhara, western Nepal. *Kathmandu University Medical Journal*, 5(17), 16–21.
- Sipic, M., Jankovic, S. V., and Jankovic, S. M. (2007). Drug utilisation patterns in Zabljak municipality, Serbia and Montenegro. *South African Family Practice*, 49(1), 16–16e. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20786204.2007.10873498>
- Soe, L. L., Htun, Y. Y., and Tin, Y. Y. (2020). *Antibacterial Drugs*

- Utilization among Patients Admitted to Medical Wards of Magway Regional Hospital.* 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.31487/j.DDA.2019.01.05>
- Soumya, M. A., Sreelekshmi, B. S., Smitha, S., Jiji, K. N., Arun, S. M., and Uma, D. P. (2015). Drug Utilization Pattern of Anti-diabetic Drugs among Diabetic Outpatients in a Tertiary Care Hospital. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res*, 8(2), 8–10.
- Tamuno, I., and Fadare, J. O. (2012). Drug Prescription Pattern in a Nigerian Tertiary Hospital. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research February*, 11(1), 146–152.
- Upadhyay, D. K., Palaian, S., Ravi, S. P., Mishra, P., and Sah, A. K. (2007). Prescribing Pattern in Diabetic Outpatients in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital in Nepal. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*, 1(4), 248–255.
- Vaniya, H. V., Darji, N. H., Patel, V. R., and Gohel, D. J. (2016). *Drug Utilization Study in Ophthalmology Outpatients in a Tertiary Care Hospital.* 4(2), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.13189/app.2016.040201>
- Vlahovic-Palcevski, V., and Bergman, B. W. U. (2002). Quality of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug prescribing in Croatia (Rijeka) and Sweden (Stockholm). *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*, 58, 209–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-002-0449-2>
- World Health Organisation. (2001). *WHO Policy Perspectives on Medicine: Globalization, TRIPS and access to pharmaceuticals.*
- World Health Organization. (1993). *How to investigate drug use in health facilities: selected drug use indicators* (WHO/DAP/93.1). World Health Organization. http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/60519/1/WHO_DAP_93.1.pdf
- World Health Organization. (1999). *Definition and diagnostic criteria for diabetes mellitu and other categories of glucose intolerance.*